

Modern approach to assessing the impact of artificial intelligence algorithms on public consciousness

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Аннотация. Для исследования актуальной проблемы в работе использован системный инструментарий, открывающий возможности для принятия адекватных ситуативных управленческих решений. В ходе экспериментального исследования категорий социальных представлений об ИИ выявлен феномен амбивалентности - наличие противоречивых тенденций в оценках общественно-значимых явлений разных групп общества об ИИ и аналогичных оценок разработчиков ИИ и специалистов финансовой сферы. При этом стремление разработчиков ИИ к унификации информации следует рассматривать как серьезную опасность для дальнейшей эволюции всего человечества. На основе прямых экспериментальных данных относительно негативного воздействия ИИ на вариативность для финансовых рынков построены прогнозы вероятного влияния ИИ на другие сферы жизнедеятельности общества. Для обобщения полученных результатов использовались хорошо известные «людские» тесты и стандартные методы оценки их результатов. Исследованы проблемы смещения оценок под влиянием манипулятивности алгоритмов ИИ с учетом факторов «индивидуализм-коллективизм» и «макиавеллизм». Они основаны на сравнительных характеристиках выборок по контрольным группам индивидов и группам условных «личностей», которые были сгенерированы ИИ. Сделан вывод о необходимости снижения негативного воздействия алгоритмов ИИ на цивилизационные ценности российского общества и целесообразности продолжения исследований манипулятивного воздействия алгоритмов ИИ на общественное сознание по другим факторам.

Abstract. To study the current problem, the work uses a system toolkit that opens up opportunities for making adequate situational management decisions. In the course of an experimental study of the categories of social ideas about AI, the phenomenon of ambivalence was revealed - the presence of contradictory trends in the assessments of socially significant phenomena of different groups of society about AI and similar assessments of AI developers and financial specialists. At the same time, the desire of AI developers to unify information should be considered as a serious danger to the further evolution of all mankind. Based on direct experimental data on the negative impact of AI on variability for financial markets, forecasts are made of the likely impact of AI on other areas of society. To generalize the results obtained, well-known "human" tests and standard methods for assessing their results were used. The problems of bias in estimates under the influence of the manipulateness of AI algorithms are studied, taking into account the factors of "individualism-collectivism" and "Machiavellianism". They are based on comparative characteristics of samples for control groups of individuals and groups of conditional "personalities" that were generated by AI. A conclusion is made about the need to reduce the negative impact of AI algorithms on the civilizational values of Russian society and the advisability of continuing research into the manipulative impact of AI algorithms on public consciousness based on other factors.

Ключевые слова: искусственный интеллект, алгоритмы, общество, сознание, вероятность манипулятивность, факторы, смещение оценок.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, algorithms, society, consciousness, probability of manipulation, factors, bias of assessments.

Introduction

The security issues of the practical use of AI algorithms are currently causing controversial debates in all layers of the global community. The key issue here is not the speed of AI development, nor the risk thresholds, but the technological capabilities

of using AI algorithms for the targeted management of public consciousness.

The authors have previously studied some aspects of the influence of AI algorithms on economic development. They substantiated the assumption that when assessing economic entities whose activities correspond to the postulates of the evolutionary

theorem of S.R. Fisher, it is impossible to use AI algorithms that narrow the diversity, since this leads to the suppression of economic growth [1]. Taking into account asymmetric errors in assessments leads to an optimal narrowing of their diversity, which is quite consistent with chaotic changes in the environment [2]. Some assessments of the influence of AI algorithms on the consciousness of various groups of people [3] led to an understanding of the need to use a differentiated approach to study the problem of narrowing diversity and biasing assessments under the influence of generative AI.

Of the available practical results of assessing the risks of the negative impact of AI on the public consciousness of China [4], the proposals on the need to test AI algorithms for compliance with “socialist values” are of the greatest interest to our study. In our opinion, this will allow us to identify targeted attempts to transform the basic values of the Russian civilizational model and shift it to the Western “Anglo-Saxon” model.

However, these and similar works by other authors do not contain systemic approaches to obtaining assessments of the impact of AI algorithms on public consciousness as a whole.

The authors believe that the problem of studying the intentional or accidental manipulability of AI algorithms, bias in assessments and narrowing of variability under their influence can be solved using sociological surveys and economic and mathematical methods. We know of many existing factors used by Russian and foreign researchers to solve this

problem. Obviously, to conduct effective testing, it is advisable to select a number of the most significant factors. This approach will fill the existing gaps in terms of conducting empirical research on the topical topic of assessing the impact of AI algorithms on public consciousness.

We have reviewed and systematized the literature in our previous work. Based on its results, approaches to selecting initial factors for analysis and tools were formed that allow us to obtain estimates of the influence of the selected factors in the plane of the topic we are studying.

Materials and methods

Ambivalence of social perceptions of AI

As a result of the studies of social representations (SR) about AI conducted by the authors, Categories of associations with ambivalent content were identified [3], [5] (see Fig. 1). Thus, in the Core of the SR structure, the Category “Fear, distrust” (negative attitude towards AI) is opposed to the Category “Faith in the good” (positive attitude towards AI), and the Category “Technological characteristics” (description of the technological characteristics of AI) is opposed to the Category “Anthropomorphism” (endowing AI with human characteristics). Consequently, the sample contains diametrically opposed groups of users in terms of value orientation with characteristic SR about AI and different behavioral attitudes. This allowed the authors to put forward a hypothesis that the consequence of the ambivalence of SR about AI was the presence in Russian society of social groups opposite to AI.

Square 1 (frequency ≥ 23; rank < 3,1) CORE	Square 3 (frequency ≥ 23; rank ≥ 3,1) PERIPHERY 1 external influence
Technological characteristics Anthropomorphism Faith in good Fear, mistrust	Archetypes
Square 2 (frequency < 23; rank < 3,1) PERIPHERY 1 Zone of potential changes	Square 4 (frequency < 23; rank ≥ 3,1) PERIPHERY 2
Temporal Characteristics	Application Resistance

Fig. 1. Results of the analysis of the SR on AI by Category.

Using lexical-metric methods, it was established that there was a wide variation in SR about AI between users. The relative commonality of SR was revealed by using the prototype analysis method with the 10% threshold in the calculation (see Fig. 1).

The presence of ambivalence in SR about AI can become a source of potential conflicts between social groups. But, at the same time, it can indicate the course of development of SR of individual groups and/or the entire society about AI. Thus, the phenomenon of SR allows not only to identify the presence of contradictory tendencies in assessments, but also to determine specific stages of their development.

The problem of narrowing variability

The ambivalence of SRs about AI may have a negative impact on its development. The authors conducted a general assessment of the adequacy of ambivalent SRs about AI in society in relation to the assessments of its developers and financial sector specialists. The revealed tendency towards

unification of information seems to be a significant danger for the progressive development of humanity.

The authors did not find any “standard” expert opinions on the problem under study. Therefore, an analogue of the parallel measurements method was used, which is successfully used in metrology to solve complex “standard-less” problems. Two groups were selected for comparison: developers of AI algorithms and financial specialists. The main objective of our study is to identify how ambivalent the assessments of the development of AI algorithms by these groups are compared to the SR of ordinary users about AI. It should be noted that our study involved non-mass groups of professionals, in contrast to the mass samples of SR assessments of Russians about AI. The existing spread in assessments of the development of AI algorithms is reflected in a number of scientific studies [6], [7], [8], [9].

Thus, the Chairman of Sberbank G. Gref outlined two directions of development of AI algorithms

[10]. In the first, AI algorithms will take over all routine functions, which will lead to mass unemployment. In the second, the development of AI algorithms will entail an increase in the number of jobs, which will entail a shortage of qualified specialists. These judgments are extremely ambivalent.

Financial experts also express mixed opinions about the development of AI algorithms. According to experts at Goldman Sachs, over the next 10 years, AI development will provide about \$7 trillion in global GDP growth [11]. At the same time, many experts believe that the accelerated development of AI algorithms is associated with great risks. Similar assessments can be made from an analysis of the dynamics of the average global growth of stocks and shares of AI companies for 2021-2023 (see Fig. 2).

The graph shown in the figure shows that financial experts believe that the prospects for accelerated development of AI algorithms are greatly overstated [12].

Opposing opinions about the risks and speed of development of AI algorithms are held by specialists from one of the most famous AI companies, OpenAI, which developed the ChatGPT chatbot, which generates texts in many languages, including Russian [13].

In contrast to these data, one can cite expectations for the value of the AI market, which will reach \$298 billion by the end of 2024. According to forecasts, in 2030, the artificial intelligence market will grow sixfold and amount to almost two trillion dollars. So far, the artificial intelligence market is growing by 20% every year [12].

Fig. 2. Dynamics of the average global growth of shares and shares of AI companies.

Given the above facts, it is safe to say that among professionals, assessments of the prospects for the development of AI algorithms are ambivalent. In this regard, the question of what to do about it is legitimate. The presence of directly opposite assessments of the development of AI algorithms significantly complicates the development of any reasonable individual and country behavior strategies.

It has already been noted above that at the level of some countries (China), measures are already being taken today to reduce the negative impact and support positive directions of AI algorithm development. The heads of large IT corporations (Microsoft, OpenAI, Google and a number of others) have spoken out in favor of testing the AI algorithms they are developing by external controllers [14]. But it is too early to talk about success in this area. This is largely due to the lack of quantitatively measurable and objective indicators.

At a meeting with young scientists, Russian President V.V. Putin raised the very important issue of diversity, which is directly related to the development of AI [15]. In his opinion, the judgments and assessments of English-language AI algorithms will

certainly be biased for Russian-speaking users. This is a serious threat to Russia.

Another example is the launch of the AI-powered Google Photos platform. In its early stages, it mistakenly sent photos of black people to the AI's "gorilla" album [16]. Similar situations can arise due to language differences. The problem of diversity narrowing by AI developers occurs in algorithmic trading [17].

In simplified form, S.R. Fisher's evolutionary theorem can be stated as follows: the rate of population adaptability is proportional to its variability. Although it is no longer considered strict in biology, it nevertheless fully reflects the problem of the influence of diversity on evolution.

For financial markets, the reduction in diversity can be measured quantitatively. Financial robots with AI have already taken up to 80-90% of the volume of stock exchange transactions. This has led to a decrease in the volatility index from 60% to 12% [18]. This is a positive fact. But there are also negative facts. They are related to the manipulation of markets by robots through spoofing and layering strategies. Thus, in 2010, the famous "flash crash" took place, when, with the help of AI algorithms, US

stock indices fell by 10% in a few minutes, and returned to their previous level in a minute and a half.

Noting the adverse impact of AI on markets, other authors believe that robots do not take into account large amounts of information about real market trends and therefore do not influence price dynamics. In other words, according to a simplified formulation of S.R. Fisher's theorem, the rate of evolution of a population is proportional to its diversity. We used this formulation because it has been reformulated many times before. In addition, modern biologists refute it because it is based on an unconfirmed assumption about the symmetry of negative and positive mutations (see, for example, [19]).

A toolkit for investigating the manipulability of AI algorithms

At present, the composition of key indicators has not yet been substantiated and there are no methods for testing AI algorithms and assessing the level of their manipulability. Therefore, we proposed using well-known methods of social psychology to assess the manipulability of AI algorithms based on the factors of "individualism-collectivism" and "Machiavellianism". With their help, groups of real people and groups of "pseudo-personalities" generated by AI algorithms were compared.

For this, the following were used:

1) a method for diagnosing the "Machiavellianism" (tendency to manipulate) of a person (hereinafter referred to as M);

2) a method for assessing the perception of civilizational values based on the factors "horizontal/vertical individualism – collectivism" (hereinafter referred to as I-C).

The tools of these methods allow us to obtain fairly reliable, dependable and valid results.

The diagnostic method of "Machiavellianism" reveals people's predisposition to manipulation in relation to the moral principles of behavior in force in society [20]. In relation to our study, "Machiavellianism" is considered as a psychological syndrome that unites cognitive, motivational and behavioral patterns of human behavior [21].

We used a questionnaire of 20 definitions with a seven-point scale. The degree of agreement or disagreement with each definition varied from "Completely agree" (7 points) to "Completely disagree" (1 point). The survey was conducted through the Anketolog service <https://anketolog.ru/> (Link to the questionnaire: <https://anketolog.ru/s/849940/LQ7fRY4K>) [1].

The second method was used to diagnose people's attitudes towards individualism and/or collectivism and their choice as basic cultural values

[22]. Our study used the questionnaire "Horizontal/vertical individualism/collectivism" [23]. This allowed us to establish the value of key indicators in terms of equality (horizontal axis) and hierarchy (vertical axis). The questionnaire included 16 definitions (4 for each axis (I-horizontal, I-vertical, K-horizontal, K-vertical)).

GPT-4 and IISbera (Giga-chat) were chosen as "pseudo-personalities" generated by AI. Both questionnaires were used sequentially for the survey.

Results and discussion

The impact of AI algorithms on the probability of survival of an economic system

To conduct the experiment and quantitatively measure the impact of AI algorithms that narrow the diversity of economic system evolution, the model proposed by the authors earlier was used [24], [25]. In concept, it is quite close to the evolutionary theorem of S.R. Fisher, but it was based only on five arguments experimentally confirmed in economics:

1) "the probability of survival" as a more universal indicator replaced adaptability;

The zero postulate of the model - the goal of any living system (including economic) is to increase the probability of its survival.

2) the probability of survival of an economic system depends on a number of factors: energy (1), information (2), material objects (3), the number (4) and quality (5) of its subjects, available natural resources (6);

3) these factors can be easily combined by the objective function through the dual concept of ownership and quantitative expression through money;

4) for the redistribution of property (the probability of survival) between the subjects of the economic system, the following rule is established: the probability of survival decreases if the subject's performance indicators are worse than the average market indicators; the probability of survival increases if the subject's performance indicators are better than the average market indicators;

5) the previous argument in terms of cost price: if the cost price of producing a product is higher than the market value, then at each exchange cycle the probability of the subject's survival will decrease until it reaches zero (bankruptcy).

The combination of these arguments allows us to construct an economic model that is close in concept to the evolutionary theorem of S.R. Fisher.

Since, for independent subjects, real nonlinear effects on deviation from the mean are not fundamental, the diversity and speed of evolution for a population of economic subjects can be expressed through a system of equations:

$$\Delta A(i) = A(i + 1) - A(i) = (\xi(i) - \langle \xi(i) \rangle) * A(i) \tag{1}$$

$$\Delta Q(i) = \Delta A(i) * I^T \tag{2}$$

where I – single factor;
 $A(i)$ – distribution of capital among entities at a given point in time i ;
 $\xi(i)$ – distribution of a certain "genetic" parameter (cost, estimation error, etc.) among subjects at a given point in time i ;
 $*$ – multiplication symbol;

$\Delta Q(i)$ – the increase in capital of the economic system at the moment i ;
 $\langle \rangle$ – symbol of capitalist averaging, depending on the distribution of A and the availability of natural resources;
 ξ – cost distribution;
 $\langle \xi(i) \rangle$ – current market value [44].

The system of equations (1) - (2) in a formalized form expresses the definition “if the performance indicators of an economic entity are below the market average, then it loses money ($\Delta B(i,j) < 0$), and otherwise, it gains ($\Delta A(i,j) > 0$)”. It allows us to establish a connection between the growth rate of ΔQ (the probability of survival) and the diversity of entities in terms of the cost of production of goods.

In the system (1) – (2), the growth of $\Delta Q(i)$ (i.e. progress) clearly depends on the “diversity” of the population, i.e. the variation coefficient ($\delta\xi(i)$). Let us

model the impact of AI algorithms that narrow the “diversity” on the market evolution by changing the volatility index from 0.6 to 0.12 (an example with financial robots). We assume that the conditional value 0 corresponds to a variation coefficient of 0.06, and 100 corresponds to a variation coefficient of 0.3. The modeling results show that the development of AI due to the narrowing of diversity leads to a decrease in the rate of economic growth (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. The effect of narrowing diversity.

To confirm these results, let's consider an example with two hypothetical countries. We assume that their economies are identical, but one country has normal variability, while the other has limited variability (due to the use of AI). Let's analyze the capitalization of these countries depending on variability. By dividing the capitalization of one country by the capitalization of the other country, we get a certain numerical indicator, which we will plot along the Z

axis. It will depend on time (scale X) and on variability (scale Y). As the variability of one of the countries increases, this indicator will grow. In one country, we will leave the variability unchanged, and in the other, we will narrow it from 60% to 12%. We get the following results.

When variability is narrowed, weak entities do not go bankrupt, but the best ones also develop inefficiently (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Evolution of a population with decreasing variability.

With normal variability, the best entities develop effectively, and the country's capitalization

grows. However, a significant portion of weak entities go bankrupt (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Evolution of a population with normal variability.

Obviously, when applied to financial markets, the use of AI reduces the variability of economic systems.

Assessing the manipulability of AI algorithms

A survey was conducted of 2 groups of AI (GPT-4 and IISber (Giga-chat)) and 2 groups of people (AI developers and financial sector specialists). The results were processed using the keys from the methods. For further research, the Mann-Whitney criterion and the Mann-Whitney U-criterion were

selected. They allowed us to identify differences in the parameter values for small samples.

It was found that there are significant differences in the M factor between GPT-4 and People, as well as between the Sber AI (Giga-chat) and People (see Fig. 6-7).

Since the asymptotic significance when comparing the calculated values for the I-K factor was greater than 0.05, there are no significant differences between the AI and People groups.

Fig. 6. GPT-4 and Humans by Factor M.

Fig. 7. Sber AI (Giga-chat) and People by factor M.

When comparing GPT-4 and Sber AI, on the one hand, and People, on the other, by the variable I, the obtained values ($U_{-emp.} = 100$ and $U_{-emp.} =$

80, respectively) lie in the range of insignificance (see Fig. 8 and 9).

Fig. 8. GPT-4 and Humans by the I factor.

Fig. 9. AI Sber and People by factor I.

When comparing GPT-4 and Sber AI, on the one hand, and People, on the other, by factor K, the obtained values ($U_{emp.} = 88$ and $U_{emp.} = 92$,

respectively) lie in the range of insignificance (see Fig. 10 and 11).

Fig. 10. GPT-4 AI and Humans by Factor K.

Fig. 11. AI Sber and People by factor K.

The presence of obvious manipulation of AI (significance by factor M) seems dangerous regardless of whether it is accidental or intentional. Insignificant deviations of the averages by factor I-K do not allow us to draw unambiguous conclusions.

Due to the limited sample of the "pseudo-personality" AI (GPT-4 and IISbera (Giga-chat)) the Fisher criterion with a standard significance level of 0.05 was used to assess the narrowing of diversity. For the studied pairs of samples, it is equal to 2.5. At the same time, for AI-1 (GPT-4) by factor M, the value $F_1 = 2.7$ was obtained and for AI-2 (IISbera (Giga-chat)) - $F_2 = 1.5$. It follows from this that there is no significant effect on the narrowing of diversity by factor M.

For the I-K factor, more specific values of the Fisher criterion were obtained: $F_1 = 5$, $F_2 = 25$. Based on these estimates, it can be concluded that there is a clearly significant influence on the narrowing of diversity for the I-K factor. In relation to the current socio-economic situation and rapidly changing external conditions, this influence seems dangerous.

Conclusion

In a constantly and randomly changing world, increasing diversity contributes to an increase in the probability of civilization survival. And therefore, the identified trend towards unification of information in the development of AI technologies poses a serious threat to the evolutionary progress of economic systems. It is already clear that the introduction of financial robots into stock trading has led not only to the displacement of people, but also to a decrease in volatility, and therefore, the profit they can earn. According to various estimates, it is about 2^{10} US dollars.

Naturally, not in all areas of human activity can specific estimates be obtained confirming that the consequence of AI development will be a narrowing of diversity. As a first approximation, to obtain them, one should use the tools of the private model developed by the authors. An important aspect is the gap in the speed of AI implementation in different areas. For example, the use of English-language AI algorithms in Russia can suppress diversity forever within one to three generations and lead to the suppression of the development of the Russian civilizational model.

The presence of ambivalent SR on AI can become a source of social conflicts. But it also testifies to the active processes of emergence of new knowledge. The aggravation of discussions and contradictory attitudes only confirm the accelerated development of AI. They can open up new opportunities and prospects for the development of AI.

In modern conditions, it is important to take into account the risks of introducing AI algorithms into everyday life of people. The negative impact of narrowing variability for situations of symmetrical "bad" and "good" deviations, as well as obviously asymmetric errors, allows us to conclude that it is advisable to use a differentiated approach to assessing the impact of AI algorithms on the consciousness of each person and society as a whole according to different factors.

Based on testing small samples, comparative results were obtained for two groups of People and two groups of "pseudo-personalities" generated by AI. When assessing AI by the I-K factor, no bias in assessments and significant narrowing of variability were found. When assessing AI by the M factor, AI algorithms differ significantly from People in terms of bias in assessments. There is an obvious need for further research to obtain more accurate estimates of the variability in factor M.

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